

LOCATE POWER METER IN DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM BASED ON POWER FLOW ANALYSIS AND VOLTAGE DROP METHOD

Muhammad Wajid Bashir

*Department of electrical and power engineering
Xian Jiaotong University
Xian Shanxi Province, China
Uetian.wajid@gmail.com*

Nomaan Khan Dasti

*School of Electronics and information Engineering
Xian Jiaotong University
Xian Shanxi Province, China
Nomaankhan016@gmail.com*

Abstract - Electricity is a major source for achieving goal of economic growth and fulfill power necessities of a nation. Electricity production has increased substantially as it has become a major requirement in a country's development, but the consumption and production of electricity should be balanced. To keep consumption synced to production, power companies are facing many hindrances and challenges due to electricity theft and wastage of electricity because of various faults and difficulties in pin pointing the exact fault location. We propose a method to analyze data of smart energy meters and determine exact location of energy meter from Transformer. It can be helpful for finding the location of power meters in distribution system. Proposed method has been tested for various power consuming nodes and it is observed that location of power meter is independent of power consumption by different nodes which is highly recommended for practical use. Our Method to analyze data depends only upon the number of consumers. Results can be improved by increasing the number of consumers. This proposed method is very convenient for maintenance, troubleshooting, minimizing the illegal usage of power and fault detection. We used power flow analysis and voltage drop technique to pin point near about exact location. Already existing method to find location by using satellite was having deficiencies as it was not accurate in indoor environment but our proposed methodology is best fit to overcome such shortcomings

Index Terms – *Smart Meter, Data Analysis, Troubleshooting, Losses Controller, Distribution system.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Power distribution system is the main heart of electricity power grid. The electricity operators generate, transmit and deliver to end consumers through the distribution system. It is the distribution system that takes high voltage power from the transmission lines, steps it down to recommended voltage for intended use by the consumers. In the hierarchical order of power grid, distribution system ranks third order, transmission system in second order and generation system is the first order. Radial networks in the distribution system is the widely used type in many industries because of its enormous advantages, not limited to easy fault detection and maintenance. Nonetheless, radial networks are more vulnerable to faults than meshed type networks.

It is evident that with new dawn of technologies on the electricity markets, such as, the use of smart systems, Internet

of Things (IOT), just to mention a few, many key players in power markets are also on the move in improving and enhancing these technologies to meet customer's expectation, by matching the consumers demand to generate supply. Many countries in Asia, America, Africa, etc., have adopted the smart technology in their respective power grid as a key drive to harness stakeholder's objectives.

A smart grid generally refers to a class of technology people are using to bring electricity delivery systems into the 21st century by using computer-based remote control and automation. These systems are made possible by two-way communication technology and computer processing that has been used for decades in other industries. Smart grids use an Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) to more efficiently support the transportation, distribution and consumption of electrical energy. It is an integrated system of smart meters, communications networks and data management systems that facilitate real-time two way communication between utilities and consumers. Thus, AMI allows utilities to access an abundance of information. This information includes electrical consumption data, load profile data, demand, time-of-use, voltage profile data and power quality data.

Smart metering has opened up new possibilities in power distribution systems. It offers more precise meter readings, earlier detection of meter failures, fraud detection, flexible billing cycles and reduced maintenance costs. An AMI can also assist with outage management, allowing utilities to detect any faults (outages) and then determine the severity and location of the outage so that they can restore power quickly. Thus, user location, fault detection and fault localization are very important.

In contrast to AMI networks, Automatic Meter Reading (AMR) networks provide one way communication from the reader to the utility and is essentially used for reporting energy usage. These are less costly but have limited capability. In many developing countries AMR rather than AMI networks are available. Current research has seen many novel developments in AMI networks rather than AMR networks especially for user location.

User Location is one of the major problems that electrical companies face as they can cause loss of electrical power to customers, property damage and, depending on the fault, can injure humans. The type of fault strongly depends on the

magnitude of the current, the location of the fault and the duration of the fault. However, 70% of the faults encountered in power grid are contributed from the distribution hierarchy 3 level. These faults are categorized into two, namely series and shunts faults. Fault can easily be minimized by knowing the location of users in distribution system.

Many researchers have done research on fault detection and analysis on the distribution networks based on the new technology of Artificial Intelligence, Analytical impedance-based method and state –estimation based. However, more is yet to be desired as the neural approach is more complex which requires extensive training.

II. METHODOLOGY

Generally distribution system is the electrical system between the transmission system and consumer meters and it is considered as a sub-station. It consists of three main parts; feeder, distributor and service mains. Distribution system supplies the electricity to consumers from transmission line. It can be divided into many types on the basis of nature of current, construction and by feeding. Figure axis labels are often a source of confusion. Use words rather than symbols. For example, as shown in Fig. 1, write “Magnetization,” or

A. Types of distribution system

- Radial distribution system
- Ring main distribution system
- Interconnected distribution system

Generally interconnected and ring main system are more expensive so they are not preferably used in power distribution system. They are not preferred in low voltage area and their construction cost is very high. Due to above these factors Radial distribution system is preferred in distribution system Applied Field (10^3 A/m)

B. Radial system:

In this system distributor is fed at one point. In simple words there is only one transformer and all other are consumers in it. In this system there is no loop, each consumer is directly connected to the main line. This is cheapest, having less complexity and least reliable network configuration. Generally radial network configuration is preferred where the transformer is located at center.

Fig. 1 Single line diagram for Radial distribution system

As this network is related to power flow analysis, power flows through network can be computed using following equations derived from single line diagram.

$$P_k = P'_{k+1} + R_k \left[\frac{(P'_{k+1})^2}{(V_{k+1})^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

Where P_k is the effective power that flows from node k to k+1, R_k is branch resistance and

$$P'_{k+1} = P_{k+1} + P_{Lk+1}$$

Where P_{Lk+1} is the real load that is connected to node k+1 and P_{k+1} is effective power that flows through node k+1.

Total power can be calculated as

$$Total\ power = \sum Power\ Loss + \sum Load\ Power \quad (2)$$

Current can be calculated through branch as

$$I_k = \frac{V_k - V_{k+1}}{R_k} \quad (3)$$

Voltage at node k+1 is calculated as

$$V_{k+1} = V_k - I_k R_k \quad (4)$$

Power loss at branch can be calculated as

$$P_{Loss} = I_k^2 \cdot R_k \quad (5)$$

Distance of consumer can be calculated using voltage drop formula

$$d = \left(\frac{V_{input} - V_k}{I \cdot R} \right) \times 4000 \quad (6)$$

Where V_{input} represent transformer voltage and I represent main current in circuit. As distance of consumer is calculated with respect to transformer so the input voltage and current will remain constant in each interval only resistance and V_k voltage will be changed.

Power flow analysis is used to calculate voltage, effective power and current with given load data and line data. For solving power flow equations there are different methods newton raphson, gaus-sidal method, fast decoupled method and backward forward sweep method. Here in this research backward forward sweep method is chosen due its less complexity, fast computation and there are some other reasons for choosing this method that are given below

- High R/X ratio
- Radial network configuration
- Unbalanced distributed load
- Unbalanced operation and multi phasing.

Backward forward sweep method is divided into two parts

A. Backward Propagation

In this sweep current and power are calculated from last node to first node then voltage convergence is checked if the load is converged then iteration are stopped otherwise voltage is

update in every iteration and these parameters are calculated. Voltage is kept constant at node during backward sweep in iteration.

B. Forward Propagation

In this method voltage is calculated using voltage drop formula with current and power flowing through circuit. This is started from first node to last node and all nodal voltages are updated. In this propagation feeder voltage is actual voltage, with the help of this voltage and current all other nodal voltages are calculate or updated.

In this method there is specified tolerance of 0.0001

$$\Delta V = V_{previous} - V_{present} \leq 0.0001 \quad (7)$$

If change in voltage is not equal or less than 0.0001 then all the real powers and current will be calculated during backward sweep and nodal voltages will be calculated during forward sweep. Iteration will be occurred until equation 7 will be satisfied. Initially voltage is set 1 to all nodes to start the operation of this method

How this backward forward sweep method works it shown in flow chart below

Fig. 2 Backward forward sweep method flow chart

B. MATLAB Simulink

III. RESULTS

In this research we have given real data of smart meters obtained from Ireland electric company. Results are obtained

using MATLAB coding and simulation with the help of above equations.

In this method we used resistance between any two smart meters is (0.05)/ (200 m). It means that theoretically distance between any two meters is 200 m. As smart meter sends data to smart grid after every 30 minutes so distance will be varied. In this method in every interval transformer current, voltage and resistance are constant only power consumed by smart meters is varying so from equation (6) it clear that distance is directly proportional to voltage difference. If the voltage difference is greater than the distance will be larger and vice versa. We did not get theoretical result during simulation because when we increased the number of users then their equivalent has been reduced. Another thing in simulation it will be very difficult to measure the resistance of power meters that's the main reason not achieving theoretical results. In this project first, thirty-three users are assumed for further analysis of a proposed method for sake of clear visibility in MATLAB Simulink

Fig. 3.1 Consumer Power Data

This graph represents the real power of smart meters at different intervals. Here T1 to T5 represents time intervals of smart meter data. In this graph, the y-axis shows the power in watt and similarly, x-axis describes the number of users. Since Smart meter has the ability of bidirectional communication between consumers and utility grid. It delivers the data of consumer to the utility grid for monitoring and billing purpose. This data is considered as an input for both coding and simulation.

Fig. 3.2 Current Profile Simulation

This graph represents the current profile users. Here T1 to T5 represents time intervals of smart meter data. In this graph, the y-axis shows the current in ampere and similarly, x-axis describes the number of users. Whenever the condition of load unbalanced occurred in distribution system there are certain variations happened in all parameters of distribution line i.e. current, voltage, power loss and distance. Current is slightly decreasing as shown in the graph. Actually why current is decreasing because resistance is increased by increasing the distance. As the distance of users is increasing from transformer their current will be decreased. Another point in the graph is that current of the first branch is larger than all other branches because power consumed by the user is large. As we know that power consumption is directly proportional to load current. so that's why there is variation in the graph at last nodes because their power is higher than other nearest nodes power. This is the main draw-back of radial distribution system farthest nodes will have to face fluctuations in voltage and current.

happens due to the the drawback of the radial system which is described in such a way that whenever load changes in distribution line, the customer at the distant end of distributor face the serious voltage fluctuations.

Fig. 3.4 Power Lose Simulation

This graph illustrates power loss obtained from simulation in different five intervals. Here T1 to T5 represents time intervals of smart meter data. In this graph, the y-axis shows the Power loss in watt and similarly, x-axis describes the number of branches. As we know that power loss is directly proportional to the square of current and resistance. Current is decreased moving away from the transformer. Due to this reason magnitude of power is maximum in the first branch then it decreased going downward. As there is variation in the graph at last nodes this is occurred due to the high power used by consumers.

Fig. 3.3 Voltage Profile Simulation

This graph depicts the voltage profile for users. Here T1 to T5 represents time intervals of smart meter data. In this graph, the y-axis shows the voltage in volts and similarly, x-axis describes the number of users. They are connected in series and away from the transformer. As these voltages are obtained using the real power of users. Every user has different power consumption at different intervals. From the graph, it is clearly shown that node one has larger voltage than all other users because it is very closest to the transformer. As the distance is increasing voltage will be slightly decreased due to voltage drop. We can also observe that voltage difference between nodes is going to smaller when we move away from transformer because of increasing resistance and smaller in the magnitude of current. There is variation in last nodes due to the variation of current as we can see in the graph of user data last three nodes have larger power consumption than their nearest nodes in the distribution line. This voltage fluctuation

Fig. 3.6 Distance Profile Simulation

This graph represents the distance profile of users in five intervals. Here T1 to T5 represents time intervals of smart meter data. Here the vertical line represents distance in different intervals similarly horizontal line shows no of consumers. This graph shows that distance is increasing from the transformer. As there is an abrupt change at the end of the graph this is due to high power consumed by the user as a

result of which current is increased also voltage is increased at those nodes.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work we find the location of power meters using the real power of power meters. We found that we can find the approximate location of power meters in distribution system, it can't be find exactly because in every interval power is changing. This method can work in every place except when there is high power used by first power meter then result are violated from theory. In future this method can be improved by making it independent to power of power meters.

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